

THE EFFECT OF USING AN ELECTRONIC TEXTBOOK IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN LABORATORY LESSONS IN CHEMISTRY

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Abstract. Today, at the main stage of reforming education, it is very important to create a new generation of educational literature that meets the requirements of modernity. In our time, new modern information technologies open up a lot of opportunities. For example, computer, printer, scanner, multiplication, animation presentation and so on. This, in turn, simplifies the creation of an active learning system and e-books. As a result, it is possible to organize modern informative lectures, practical and experimental laboratories.

Key words: innovative technologies, animation, audio-sounds, video lessons, ICT.

ЭФФЕКТ ПРИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИИ ЭЛЕКТРОННОГО УЧЕБНИКА В ВУЗЕ ЛАБОРАТОРНЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ ПО ХИМИИ

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Аннотация. Сегодня, на основном этапе реформирования образования, очень актуально создание учебной литературы нового поколения, отвечающей требованиям современности. В наше время новые современные информационные технологии открывают массу возможностей. Например, компьютер, принтер, сканер, умножение, анимационная презентация и так далее. Это, в свою очередь, упрощает создание активной системы обучения и электронных книг. В результате можно организовать современные информативные лекции, практические и экспериментальные лаборатории.

Ключевые слова: инновационные технологии, анимация, аудио-звуки, видео уроки, ИКТ.

The national personnel training program is one of the urgent and priority tasks of our time in preparing young people for a new social environment, educating them in the spirit of the times. In our country, the application of modern pedagogical information technologies to the educational process is developing in order to organize the educational process on a scientific basis, speed it up and increase efficiency. The use of modern information technologies in the organization of chemistry lessons gives good and effective results compared to the traditional method. Reforming and improving the education system of Uzbekistan in the 21st century is one of the priority tasks. This, in turn, requires our chemical scientists to update the educational literature on academic subjects, taking into account modern requirements and the latest achievements of science, to introduce innovative and educational technologies into the educational process [1].

The application of information and communication technologies (ICT) opens up new perspectives and opportunities for teaching chemistry. In addition, the development of the ability to read independently, focusing on specific literacy in working with information sources, is a necessary condition for the intellectual development of a student [2].

The purpose of the work is the use of information and communication technologies in chemistry. Homework assignments can be assigned remotely by the teacher, and completed assignments can be checked by the student. ICT is the most convenient way to manage educational material.

Distinctive features of information innovation technologies:

- innovative technologies always increase the interest of schoolchildren and students in science;

- In the process of applying innovative technologies, a culture of communication between schoolchildren and students develops;
- Innovative technologies allow schoolchildren and students to show their talents and knowledge;
- Forms positive qualities and qualities of pupils and students.

An electronic textbook is a software and methodological complex that automatically creates the possibility of teaching a subject or part of it by the teacher himself using a computer.

Electronic textbooks should contain complete information on the subject or topic and should not be reproduced using animation or video images, enriched and filled with audio text. In addition to the use of multimedia technologies, an electronic textbook should be convenient for individual use by the reader or student. It can serve as a ready-made consultation for students. It follows that the electronic textbook should be in a continuous and ordered sequence. Any chosen topic or section can be effective and efficient only if it is supplemented with practical exercises and an exam (test).

The electronic chemistry textbook mainly consists of 5 parts.

1. Display text on the computer.
2. Presentation (multimedia) organization - animations are shown here.
3. Test control - theoretical knowledge on the subject is evaluated.
4. Basic phrases are given for each topic.
5. Scientists who have contributed to the science of chemistry are provided with information.

By creating an e-book, the student can have the following options:

1. Quickly search for the necessary lecture and laboratory work according to the plan (it is difficult to find it in a regular textbook);
2. Audio and video views that are not found in books and textbooks: see and hear the phenomena that occur in experiments - gas separation, combustion of substances, color of the precipitate, its melting on video using live sound, color images and music;
3. Animated viewing of reaction equations and experiments on the topic;
4. Animated viewing of the structure and images of chemical formulas, schemes;
5. Printing the necessary parts of the text on the printer;
6. Consolidation of the knowledge gained at the lecture and a quick check (for example, a test, problem solving, filling out a table);
7. Knowledge of important historical dates in the field of chemistry;
8. They will be able to get acquainted with scientists who conducted research in the field of chemistry, see them, get information about them.

Therefore, it is important to apply new innovative pedagogical technologies using advanced and modern teaching methods for students to master the science of "Physical Chemistry". The student uses electronic textbooks, multimedia and animation to master the subject [3, 4]. In addition to saving the student's time, the electronic textbook allows you to reuse materials that are difficult for students to understand. It follows from this that it is desirable to place hypertexts in the form of an alphabet or in the form of a "tree". In comparison, in a regular textbook, the reference is given to the page number, while in the electronic textbook, it takes a lot of work to enter laboratory exercises and a control type in the text, animation, and video sequence sorting mechanism. The most important issue here is to ensure consistency and continuity. In this case, instructions on how to use the electronic textbook can be given. Instructions may be provided on paper or as a file called "readme", as individual animations, or as HTML, FLASH and other documents.

The database tutorials are mostly developed in Borland Delphi and Visual C++ and contain a very large database. Such textbooks are mainly used in biology, physics, chemistry and similar subjects and fields of science where the database can be widely used. The main goal of our database application is that we can reduce the size of the e-textbook [5].

Most people think of e-textbooks as text written on a computer. But with the use of modern technologies, such an electronic textbook has been created, which is given with the help of sound and moving animation. E-textbooks in HTML format are among the textbooks that mainly use a lot of text and fewer images and videos [6]. The advantage of electronic textbooks in this form is that they are easy to use and print, and they do not require special instructions. Such textbooks mainly consist of hypertexts and are distinguished by the small size of textbooks, as well as the ability to quickly search for information. Internet Explorer is required to use this guide.

At present, an electronic textbook for laboratory classes in bioorganic chemistry has been created at the Department of Organic and Physical-Colloid Chemistry.

For the first time, methods of using multimedia were developed in order to convey information about visual experiments to students in electronic classes of laboratory chemistry classes, and they were used to consolidate the skills and abilities of students in the classroom. Laboratory electronic textbook of bioorganic chemistry consists of 6 chapters, more than 60 animations (sound and moving), more than 100 tests, 10 slides and glossaries. Figure 1 shows a fragment from the video of the laboratory work on the topic "Protein Denaturation". Such videos of laboratory work are available in each chapter, it is convenient for students to do their own work [7].

Picture. 1. Fragment from the video of the laboratory work

These electronic textbooks are mainly developed in the form of special programs in the form of HTML, various Web sites, FLASH, Borland Delphi, Visual C ++.

Now, with the help of the above special programs, we have set a goal to create an electronic textbook on physical chemistry.

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